

Wall-to-Wall Worker Organizing in the University: The Coalition of Rutgers Unions

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Abstract: Workers at Rutgers University, the state university of New Jersey, USA, have formed the Coalition of Rutgers Unions (CRU). This workplace-based union coalition engages in wall-to-wall organizing, which seeks to include every Rutgers worker, irrespective of occupation, status, or union affiliation. This form of coalition creatively retains the benefits of certified unions while navigating the sectionalism encouraged by American labour laws. CRU's recovery of traditional organizing principles amid neoliberal conditions is a new industrial unionism. It is thereby an example of the union renewal affirmed by proponents of social movement unionism. CRU is also an organizational model for workers in large, complex, heterogenous workplaces with multiple existing unions. This article draws from qualitative interviews with CRU activists to discuss its participants, structure, activities, and its role in a victorious 2023 strike at Rutgers University.

Keywords: Higher education; industrial unionism; wall-to-wall; union renewal; union coalitions

Introduction

The Coalition of Rutgers Unions (CRU) is a bold experiment in union renewal. CRU is a workplace-based, cross-union coalition at Rutgers University, the state university of New Jersey, USA. Like all higher education institutions, Rutgers has a diverse and stratified workforce which includes tenured and adjunct faculty, graduate student workers, administrative staff, health care professionals, tradespeople, food service workers, and custodians. They are represented by twenty unions across Rutgers' three main campuses (Appendix A). CRU attempts to overcome sectional divisions between these workers through 'wall-to-wall' organizing, which seeks to unite all workers in a workplace irrespective of differences in their form of work, skill, status, or identity. This workplace-based union coalition engages in coordinated collective bargaining and strikes, joint campaigns, political education, and resource sharing. CRU not only brings together the best-paid and most secure workers with the worst-paid and most precarious, but pursues actions that emphasize the issues of the latter, such as a worker-led work-sharing project during the COVID-19 pandemic that prevented layoffs for food service workers and adjunct faculty. This solidarity was most evident in CRU's contributions to a 2023 strike by three Rutgers unions, which prioritized substantial gains for the most precarious workers. CRU is not without significant internal tensions and some persisting shortcomings, but its wall-to-wall organizing is reviving—and innovating upon—the industrial unionism that drove the American labour movement at its peak.

The recovery of traditional labour organizing principles must contend with American labour laws, which channel unions toward a sectionalist focus on the narrow interests of their own members, through provisions like state-defined bargaining units that separate workers into confined 'communities of interest' or prohibitions against solidarity strikes between unions (McCartin, 2017; Moody, 1988). Complacent unions often accepted the legal constraints which attended labour rights, leading to a decline of organizing capacities that left the labour movement completely unprepared for the intensified attacks on such rights by both government and employers in the neoliberal era (Gindin 2013; Moody, 1988).

The long-term declines in American union density and workplace conditions (Aronowitz 2014; Lichtenstein, 2002) have inspired a wide-ranging debate about union renewal (Kumar and Schenk, 2006). Some participants have argued for campaigns to 'organize the unorganized' in order to recover union density (Russo and Banks, 1996; SEIU, 2003). Nevertheless, the insufficiency of this overly quantitative focus is shown by those sectors that, despite their relatively high density, have been unable to prevent the neoliberal restructuring and degradation of their working conditions, such as the public universities that are the focus of this article (House and Gray, 2019; Johnson et al., 2003). Indeed, given the sectionalism encouraged by American labour laws, high union density in a sector or even a specific workplace can often mean the existence of several unions that do not meaningfully collaborate. Other participants in the union renewal debate emphasize a more qualitative focus on the kinds of unions into which workers are organizing, particularly those advocates of a 'social movement unionism' that

recovers traditions of industrial organizing (Moody, 1997; Fletcher and Hurd, 2001; Nissen, 2003). In the same way that the original mass political parties were described as such not merely for their size but because of the substantial participation they demanded from their regular members (Krouwel, 2006), industrial unions engaged in wall-to-wall organizing not only to increase the collective power of workers, but to enact principles of equality that raised the worst-off to a higher and more commonly shared dignity (Eisenscher, 2002; Matles and Higgins, 1974; Foster, 1937). We argue that recent attempts to recover these traditional organizing principles amid neoliberal conditions are a new industrial unionism.

Wall-to-wall organizing in large and complex workplaces faces unique challenges (House and Gray, 2019). These workplaces can feature vast divisions of labour, diverse forms of work, and significant inequalities between workers. They might also have multiple existing unions which, like much of the broader labour movement, rarely collaborate. This is particularly true if there are workers who traditionally identify as ‘professionals’ more than as workers. In general, higher unionization rates among such workers mean only a greater occupational consciousness, not a higher class consciousness, if they merely protect their own privileged status within the workforce (Ross, Savage, and Watson, 2020). Such workplaces, especially where there has been significant subcontracting, might also contain numerous employers, including one overarching authority, a ‘super-employer,’ that has agreements with the other employers in the workplace (House and Gray, 2019). Multiple employers in the same workplace can further fragment workers’ responses when, for example, they play into often opaque and overlapping webs of jurisdictional authority in order to defuse the demands made by separate groups of workers across the workplace. Workplace-based union coalitions are an attempt to address these challenges in large and complex workplaces. For example, they have been proposed for hospitals (McAlevey, 2014). In prior research on an airport workers’ council, we argued that this model could also be applied to workplaces like shopping malls and university campuses (House and Gray, 2019). In this article, we contend that the subsequent emergence of CRU has become an important case of the latter. Indeed, as we argue here, CRU joins other education workers, such as the Chicago Teachers’ Union, West Virginia public school teachers, California graduate student workers, and the new national organization, Higher Education Labor United, in putting this sector in the vanguard of the American labour movement.

The workplace-based union coalition is a form of new industrial unionism that creatively maneuvers around the sectionalism encouraged by American labour law. In the union renewal debate, commentators often point to union coalitions as a key strategy because of their transformative effects on the unions that participate in them (Tattersall, 2005; Frege and Kelly, 2003). But these commentators typically refer to coalitions between a union and non-union community organizations, such as social movement groups. There is much less research on coalitions between unions within the same workplace, a gap in the literature which this article seeks to fill. Unlike recent proposals for alternative labour organizations that are based in geographic areas rather than specific workplaces, such coalitions cede neither the industrial power that is found in the workplace nor the consummate industrial action: strikes (McAlevey, 2016). Workplace-based union coalitions use their workplace power in a new form of worker representation. Furthermore, this potential power is enhanced in a strategic industry like the education sector, which cannot be easily off-shored and is so integral a part of local economies

(Wolfson and O'Connell, 2020; Baldwin, 2021). For these reasons, since these union coalitions are workplace-based, they are class-rooted, and because they attempt to organize all workers in a workplace as workers, they are class-focused.

In this article, we argue that CRU is a model for union renewal that implements a unique form of social movement unionism. In particular, we contend that it is a leading case of the new industrial unionism because it pursues wall-to-wall organizing in a large and complex workplace with a stratified workforce and many existing unions. We analyze its successes, such as its work-sharing project, its community unionism, and in particular, the coordinated strikes of 2023, each of which has achieved collaboration among traditionally disjointed groups by prioritizing the issues of the most vulnerable among them. We also go into substantial detail about CRU's shortcomings. Insofar as the coalition is becoming an increasingly influential model for American education workers and beyond, attempts to replicate its organizational form and activities elsewhere will likely encounter similar challenges. We focus specifically on the informality and persisting cleavages in its organizational structure, its fraught attempts to navigate widely disparate union cultures, including tensions between participating union locals and their parent unions, and, despite its best efforts, its related difficulties in retaining participation by unions that disproportionately represent blue collar, racialized, and gendered campus workers.

The rest of this article has six parts. First, we canvas debates about union renewal and argue for a recovery of industrial unionism. Second, we discuss examples of a new industrial unionism in the education sector, including CRU. Third, we explain our research design and methods. Fourth, we map the Rutgers workplace and the differences, inequalities, and tensions between workers that CRU must confront in its wall-to-wall organizing. Fifth, we analyze CRU's organizational structure and activities. Finally, we discuss the 2023 Rutgers strike, which provides a rich case for assessing CRU's strengths and weaknesses.

Union Renewal and Industrial Unionism

Since the 1970s, American union density has dramatically declined while precarity, work intensity, and underemployment have risen (Aronowitz 2014; Lichtenstein, 2002). This has sparked debates about union renewal, which feature three major perspectives (Kumar and Schenk, 2006).

First, the value-added perspective argues that, in the heightened competition of the new global economy, unions can maintain relevance by adding value to their employers and fostering labour-management cooperation (Rubinstein, 2002; Kochan and Osterman, 1994). Higher education provides compelling counter-evidence to this strategy of 'progressive competitiveness.' The cooperation to which this perspective aspires already existed between faculty and administrations in the higher education boom of the postwar period, but in the neoliberal era, administrations have gradually eroded this collegial governance with few prospects for reversal (Angulo, 208; Butler et al., 2017). This more adversarial relation provoked

many faculty to increasingly identify as workers who need unions, rather than professionals with mere associations (DeCew, 2003).

Second, the ‘organizing the unorganized’ perspective is critical of service unionism, whereby unions treat grievances and bargaining like services exchanged for the dues of otherwise passive members (Russo and Banks, 1996; SEIU, 2003; see also: Carter, 2000). Instead, this perspective holds that unions should not only service existing members, but should mobilize them in ambitious unionization drives, protests, and strikes. Nevertheless, this perspective focuses on overly quantitative considerations. In higher education, even those institutions with very high union density have been unable to prevent neoliberal restructuring (Johnson et al., 2003). This is true also of workplaces with high levels of militancy, such as airports (House and Gray, 2019). If these levels are the future to which union renewal advocates aspire, we must note the shortcomings of a high union coverage that is split between fragmented and factious unions who pursue only their own sectional interests.

Third, and the perspective to which this article contributes, is social movement unionism (Moody, 1997; Fletcher and Hurd, 2001; Nissen, 2003). Proponents argue for more qualitative considerations of the kinds of unions into which workers are organizing. They draw from the broader social movement literature to argue for more participatory unions that integrate their struggles with broader social movements and issues affecting workers as a class. This perspective, also known as social unionism or social justice unionism, is a contested concept (Ross, 2007), but in this article, we agree with those thinkers who regard social movement unionism as a recovery of the principles of industrial unionism (Eisenscher, 2002).

In the early twentieth century, industrial unions emerged to challenge established craft unions, whose sectionalism excluded semi-skilled and unskilled workers (Matles and Higgins, 1974). Industrial unionists affirmed a ‘one plant-one union’ principle that included all workers, regardless of skill, race, sex, or nationality (Foster, 1937). This anti-sectionalist commitment to wall-to-wall organizing grounds the other principles of industrial unionism: democratic and participatory unions; workers engaging in, and learning through, direct action; the importance of strikes; expanding workers’ control over production; the inherent antagonism of labour and capital; rooting workplace struggles in broader social issues affecting the class as whole; and, among the most active organizers, advocating for an independent political party of labour that envisions an alternative to capitalism (Eisenscher, 2002).

The unionization wave of the 1930s was more of a cause than an effect of modern American labour legislation. Indeed, union recognition through strikes, rather than legal certification, remained prevalent even in the few years after the passage of the National Labor Relations Act of 1935, also known as the Wagner Act, which established the mandatory recognition of unions, collective bargaining, and strikes (Freeman, 1998). The Roosevelt administration responded to this industrial unionization wave, as did several influential national labour leaders, by seeking to enshrine rights for workers in ways that also channeled their activities into more conciliatory forms. While organizing efforts were supported by national labour organizations like the Congress of Industrial Organizations (CIO), and, to some extent, the American Federation of Labor (AFL), rank-and-file workers, local union leaders, and organizers from various socialist organizations were often the key driving force (Stepan-Norris and Zeitlin, 2002; Goldfield and Melcher, 2019; Freeman, 1998).

Industrial unionism thereby contends with constraints imposed by American labour law. Wagner encourages a sectionalism that often approximates craft unionism, because government-defined collective bargaining units separate different groups of workers according to a ‘community of interests’ (McCartin, 2017; Moody, 1988). This is replicated in most of the state legislation that regulates public education workers (DeCew, 2003). Preventing workers from deciding who to include in their own units hinders the wall-to-wall organizing typical of industrial unionism. This is particularly true for workers in large and heterogeneous workplaces, such as universities. Highly legalistic collective bargaining and grievance procedures also encouraged union bureaucracy as an alternative to shopfloor organizing and militancy (Herberg, 1943). The Taft-Hartley Act of 1947, which prohibited sympathy strikes and secondary boycotts, reinforced Wagner’s inherent sectionalism and legalism (Moody, 1988).

These constraints, however, are not entirely external. A basic premise shared by every union renewal perspective is that unions are partly responsible for their decline—that is also why they are capable of renewing themselves (Kumar and Schenk, 2006). Many workers accepted the legal terms of unionization, especially amid a postwar economic boom in which sectionalism and legalism were still compatible with gains in compensation and working conditions (Gindin 2013). This fostered a decline in workers’ organizing capacities, which left the labour movement unprepared in the transition to the neoliberal period that saw renewed and intensified attacks on labour rights and working conditions by employers and governments (Moody, 1988).

Unions remain necessary, but certain forms of unionism can demobilize workers, set them into competition with each other, and be serious impediments to their collective power (Gindin, 2013). This is why, in the neoliberal period, the ‘value-added’ perspective on union renewal, which denies the antagonism between labour and employers, contributes to *class decomposition*. Furthermore, unionized workers must navigate an extremely cluttered field of labour relations in which the sectionalism encouraged by labour law is exacerbated by ‘competitive unionism’ (Gindin, 2013). Therefore, the ‘organizing the unorganized’ perspective, if it is not combined with efforts to also transform unions and the labour movement, contributes to *class fragmentation*. It is the social movement unionism perspective which holds the best prospect for union renewal, because, in attempting to overcome the sectionalism of unions, it contributes to *class formation*. We argue that this attempt to recover traditional organizing principles in neoliberal conditions is a new industrial unionism.

CRU is only one of a few such initiatives in the US. For example, during COVID-19, the United Electrical Workers joined the Democratic Socialists of America to form the Emergency Workplace Organizing Committee, which offered organizer training and support to over 2,000 essential workers, regardless of employer or location, and in 2023 alone connected 65 workplace campaigns to unions (Blanc, 2024). In another example, the revitalized United Auto Workers (UAW) has inspired trade unionists throughout the US (Lichtenstein, 2024). Their innovative “stand up strikes” against Ford, General Motors, and Stellantis used a rolling strike strategy to selectively target whichever employer was being most intransigent in bargaining. The UAW not only made major wage gains after years of concessions, but more importantly, ended the two-tier wages dividing newer union members from senior ones. There have also been attempts to engage in new industrial unionism in the education sector.

New Industrial Unionism in the Education Sector

The education sector is, in many ways, in the vanguard of the American labour movement. Despite the incredibly de-centralized system of US labour relations, recent victories by education workers in particular jurisdictions have influenced other workers across the country. The Chicago Teachers' Union (CTU) has been particularly significant. After a reform group, the Caucus of Rank-and-File Educators, won control of the CTU in 2010, their community organizing with parents and students prepared their successful 2012 strike, which foregrounded community-wide issues (McAlevy, 2016). This sparked renewed interest in community unionism throughout the American labour movement. In West Virginia, a state where public sector strikes are illegal, rank-and-file public school teachers launched a wildcat strike in 2018, which garnered widespread community support and won wage increases substantially beyond those originally offered (Blanc, 2019). This renewed militancy sparked a 'Red State Revolt' by teachers in other primarily Republican states with similarly restrictive labour laws, including Oklahoma and Arizona.

There have also been dramatic developments in American higher education. Many administrations used the COVID-19 pandemic to accelerate neoliberal restructuring by forcing through unpopular reforms in the name of crisis mitigation (Rhoades, 2021). In response, higher education workers are fighting back on a scale not seen in a generation or more (Schirmer and Tarlau, 2022). In 2022, work stoppages in the education sector reached a 20-year peak (Iafolla, 2023) and education workers were more than 60% of all striking workers (Kallas et al., 2022). Campus workers are also joining unions in droves. 30,000 graduate student workers filed for union elections in 2022 alone (Watanabe, 2023). This continues a recent unionization wave among graduate workers and adjunct faculty, particularly by national unions not traditionally associated with the education sector (Tolley, 2018). 48,000 graduate workers at the University of California, affiliated with the UAW, won substantial wage increases after launching the largest strike in the history of higher education (Lichtenstein, 2022).

Seizing this momentum, a new national coalition, Higher Education Labor United (HELU), held its inaugural convention in July 2021, hosting participants from over a hundred locals, and held its founding convention in May 2024 (HELU, n.d.). CRU activists have been instrumental in its founding and development (Gavigan, AAUP-AFT, Executive Council). HELU envisions cross-sectoral organizing that challenges the regional sectionalism currently pervading higher education unionism (HELU, n.d.). It creates space for broadly political demands, such as free universal higher education, and, as part of its industrial unionism strategy, it promotes wall-to-wall organizing open to all education workers, irrespective of job, rank, or status. Indeed, HELU's slogan is, 'Wall-to-wall, coast-to-coast' (Worthen, 2022).

This wave of activity in the education sector provides the context in which numerous groups of higher education workers have attempted wall-to-wall organizing in particular workplaces. These efforts can be categorized into three broad types. This is new industrial unionism by (1) singular certified unions; (2) singular uncertified unions; and (3) multiple certified unions in the same workplace.¹ After briefly canvassing the first two types, the rest of this article will focus on CRU as our case study of the third type.

The first type of new industrial unionism has occurred in workplaces where a single certified union can represent all or most of the workers. This is extremely rare in the large and heterogeneous workplaces typical of higher education. The key example is the Professional Staff Congress at City University of New York (PSC-CUNY), which represents full-time and part-time faculty, professional staff, and graduate student workers. After a long period of unequal structures and practices, during which adjuncts seriously considered disaffiliation, PSC-CUNY has recently renewed itself along anti-sectionalist principles (Elliott-Negri, 2018; Rhoades, 2021). The union does not include blue collar campus workers, however, a persistent problem for wall-to-wall organizing in higher education.

There are also recent examples of the second type of new industrial unionism by uncertified unions. In some places, particularly anti-union ‘right-to-work’ states,² American labour laws prohibit union security agreements. In others, workers choose to forego the potential benefits of certified unions in order to avoid the legal constraints that dictate bargaining units, enshrine management rights, and curtail the ability to strike. In either case, workers form “solidarity unions” that emphasize direct action to pressure employers to meet workers’ demands (Lynd, 1992). In higher education, the key example is the United Campus Workers (UCW), affiliated with the Communications Workers of America (CWA). On numerous Southern campuses in right-to-work states, UCW has formed ‘minority unions’ that are without legal recognition, but also avoid state labor boards dictating bargaining units according to a ‘community of interest’ (United Campus Workers, n.d.; Rhoades, 2021). As such, UCW organizes across job ranks and categories. Their chapters include faculty, staff, and student workers. They call this ‘wall-to-wall organizing without collective bargaining rights.’

The third type of new industrial unionism features multiple certified unions in a single workplace. Workers have discovered that wall-to-wall organizing in such conditions requires a coalition of unions based in the workplace. By organizing across occupational categories, legal bargaining units, and union affiliations, they retain the benefits of recognized unions while creatively navigating the sectionalism encouraged by American labour laws. Such union coalitions have also been attempted in hospitals (McAlevey, 2014) and airports (House and Gray, 2019).

The key example of a workplace-based union coalition in higher education is CRU, the focus of this article. CRU participants describe it as a form of industrial unionism (Kumar, 2023). They draw from past industrial organizing in the education sector (Murch and Wolfson, 2023), such as Howard University, a historically Black research university, where faculty and non-faculty employees organizing with the CIO achieved union recognition at the same time in 1945, a first in the history of American higher education (see Cain, 2012).

A crucial strategy in the union renewal literature, especially for that perspective dedicated to social movement unionism, is union coalitions, because of the transformative effects that participation in coalitions can have on unions (Tattersall, 2005; Frege and Kelly, 2003). Typically, scholars refer to unions forming coalitions with non-union organizations. Indeed, some of the more influential definitions of union coalitions exclude coalitions between unions (Frege et al., 2003). Furthermore, alliances between unions typically refer to labour councils, which are based on geographic region or are industry wide. Thus, there is a relative gap in the literature about coalitions between unions in the same workplace, particularly in decentralized

labour regimes with little sectoral bargaining (however, see: House and Gray, 2019; McAlevey, 2014; Walsh, 1994). This article seeks to fill that gap. These coalitions are not the same thing as coordinated or coalition bargaining (Eaton et al., 2008; Woodward, 1972). Although workplace-based union coalitions might engage in these tactics, bargaining is not their sole purpose. They are permanent organizations that seek to maintain the same levels of activity between rounds of bargaining.

This kind of coalition is based in workplace power, which includes the leverage provided by the potential for production-halting strikes. CRU has the additional workplace power of being a strategic industry, because the education sector, like much of the public sector, cannot be offshored, which eliminates a threat often levelled against private sector workers (McAlevey, 2016). CRU, like the Chicago Teachers' Union, has used this strategic workplace power as the hub from which to develop robust community unionism. Indeed, CRU utilizes even more of a strategic industry because of the outsized influence of higher education campuses: they are often a leading employer in their communities (Wolfson and O'Connell, 2020; Baldwin, 2021). This greatly compounds the disruptive potential for actions like strikes. Furthermore, CRU goes beyond the CTU's alliances with blue-collar public school workers, because, with a workplace-based union coalition, CRU attempts to create a fully wall-to-wall organization. Ultimately, we argue that CRU provides a model for union renewal in large and complex workplaces featuring heterogeneous forms of work, particularly if workers are already divided into multiple existing unions.

Research Design and Methods

This study draws on qualitative interviews. We identified among the twenty Rutgers unions (Rutgers Office of University Labor Relations, n.d.) those with publicly declared affiliations with CRU (Rutgers AAUP-AFT, n.d.a). We contacted activists who, in their popular writing and media appearances, were most prominently associated with CRU, and then used snowball sampling to contact other important participants from different bargaining units and relevant community organizations. We also used snowball sampling and publicly available contact information to reach representatives of unions that had limited or no involvement in CRU. Finally, we contacted both the President and the Vice-President of University Labor Relations at Rutgers University.

We conducted interviews with a total of nine participants from six different bargaining units (Appendix B). Their unions actively participate in CRU, representing education, health care, and information technology workers. Five interview participants are elected union leaders, three are staff, and one is a rank-and-file activist. When we cite interview participants, we note their union and role. We conducted semi-structured, qualitative interviews. Our preliminary interview script focused on labour relations at Rutgers University; CRU's structure, activities, and goals; and their own relation to, and evaluation of, CRU. The interviews occurred between 12 December 2022 and 24 March 2023.

This study has some limitations. We secured interviews only with the most active current CRU participants. Several important unions declined interviews, including the American Federation of State, County and Municipal Employees (AFSCME) Local 888; the International Brotherhood of Teamsters Local 97; and the Union of Rutgers Administrators–American Federation of Teachers (URA-AFT). The Rutgers University administration also declined to participate. Our interview data therefore skews toward the perspectives of academic, healthcare professional, and white-collar workers. The perspectives of blue-collar workers, especially those in the lowest paid and most precarious jobs, is a particular gap in this study.

The uneven participation in this study corresponds to the uneven participation in CRU. The interview participants regard CRU as an integral part of their labour activism. Furthermore, most interview participants differentiated their own unions from the ‘business unions’ at Rutgers. In general, these differences exist more on a spectrum than as a set of rigid categories (Ross, 2007), but business unions tend toward centralized leaderships, passive memberships, an exclusive focus on bargaining and servicing collective agreements, and disinterest in broader social issues (Fantasia, 2004). This helps to explain their limited participation in projects like CRU and it is likely relevant to their lack of participation in this study. CRU’s attempts to overcome this divide between union cultures is explored in more substance below.

Mapping Rutgers University

Workplace mapping is an organizing tool. It tracks every group of workers that must be included in wall-to-wall organizing, the current causes of division between them, and the potential sources of solidarity (McAlevey, 2016). Industrial unionism in higher education confronts workplaces with wide variations in occupational category, status, and conditions. If workers are unionized, there are almost always multiple units and different unions. Furthermore, the subcontracting that has become increasingly common for cleaning and food services multiplies employers and corresponding units. Mergers with other educational or health institutions can also mean different already existing units for the same kinds of work. Therefore, in higher education, labour relations can be extremely balkanized. Across Rutgers’ three campuses, there are around 30,000 employees, 20,000 of which are members of twenty unions (Givan, 2021; Rutgers AAUP-AFT, n.d.b; O’Dea, 2023; see Appendix A).

The group with the most structural power is full-time faculty, despite experiencing degraded working conditions in the neoliberal period. Their association gained full collective bargaining rights in 1970. In an unusually early case in American higher education, graduate student workers unionized in 1972 (Rutgers AAUP-AFT, n.d.b). Rarer still, they joined the same union as full-time faculty. The gulf between tenured and adjunct faculty, who also have their own AAUP chapter, shows the hierarchies between occupationally similar workers that industrial unionism must confront (Powelson, 2011).

Professional status has often been a kind of craft union barrier to university workers’ unity (Ross, et al., 2020). While this sectionalism is most often associated with tenured

professors, Mattson describes a ‘botched campaign’ to organize Rutgers administrative employees in the late 1990s:

I was startled by a question many of them asked before they would sign a card to hold an election: ‘We’re not going to become a part of that labor union that represents the janitors, are we?’ God forbid, I would always think to myself, that we librarians, research directors, and secretaries would actually consort with such trash—that was always the not-so-hidden message behind these comments. (2003, 94-95).

Nevertheless, administrators eventually unionized in 2007 (URA-AFT, n.d.). A sense of elevated professional status can also persist among other campus workers, such as information technology and healthcare workers (Novosielski, HPAE, Co-President; Tsitouras, AAUP-BHSNJ, Executive Director; Holden, CIR-SEIU, staff). With respect to the latter, Rutgers’ history of mergers with educational and health institutions means there are three unions for academic workers in the medical field and four unions for professional practitioners.

Structural inequalities further complicate university workers’ unity. Faculty supervise graduate students in their roles as students and as workers. Furthermore, some members of CWA Local 1031 supervise some members of Health Professionals and Allied Employees (HPAE) (Hernandez, CWA 1031, Vice-President).

Rutgers’ blue-collar workforce includes food service, custodial, maintenance, and trades workers, as well as unionized police and firefighters. Like the white-collar workforce, among blue-collar workers there are full-time, permanent employees who are relatively well-compensated, as well as part-time and contractual employees with meagre compensation and precarious conditions. These status inequalities intersect with others: the workers engaged in part time, contractual employment, whether academic or non-academic, are disproportionately racialized, women, and immigrants (Kumar, 2023).

There are also significant differences in the kinds of unions that campus workers form. Some tend toward social movement unions while others tend toward business unions. The latter disproportionately represent blue collar and service workers (Martino, AAUP-AFT, member; O’Hea, HPAE, Co-President; Hernandez, CWA 1031, Vice-President).

Industrial organizing must also face legacies of failed solidarity. In 1987, the AAUP crossed an AFSCME picket line, which rankles many to this day (Narvaez, 1987; Novosielski, HPAE, Co-President). In other cases, there are debates about the very nature of solidarity. Longstanding criticisms of police unions, bolstered by recent mass movements against systemic racism, have inspired some campus workers to exclude campus police from their wall-to-wall organizations (United Campus Workers Colorado, 2020).

The various sources of division and sectionalism between these workers contribute to class fragmentation or even decomposition. But they can be confronted with one common ground for solidarity which can provide the basis for class formation, namely, the way in which neoliberal restructuring has degraded the conditions for every group of workers across the higher education sector. As state and private revenues for higher education have decreased, especially since the economic downturn of the 1970s, austerity measures have meant fewer staff, less

resources, larger classes, heavier teaching loads, and overall declines in the quality of instruction (Angulo, 2018; Johnson, et al., 2003). Although tuition fees have risen dramatically, these have gone toward a bloated administration, not the educators, who are increasingly precariously employed adjunct faculty, nor the staff (Tolley, 2018). Furthermore, non-teaching staff, especially custodial, food service, and front-line administrative workers, also face precarity through downsizing and subcontracting (Rhoades and Maitland, 1998). These are the conditions which CRU must navigate in its attempts to build a wall-to-wall organization.

CRU's Participants, Structure, and Activities

CRU, in its current form, began during the COVID-19 pandemic. The coalition hosts regular meetings for participating unions to discuss common issues, choose joint demands, and coordinate collective actions (Wolfson, AAUP-AFT, President; Givan, 2021). To the extent that participants are able to work with and through existing unions, CRU is an example of a new form of worker representation that unites workers in large, complex, and divided workplaces with a high degree of union density. Its coalition form cedes neither the strategic site of the workplace nor the leverage of potential strike actions—factors that make it a potentially important model for other similar workplaces. In this section, we will examine the participants and their relationships with the coalition before turning to CRU's organizational structure and activities.

Although CRU aspires to become a truly wall-to-wall organization, it has not secured the participation of every Rutgers union. The participants are primarily academic workers, administrative staff, and health care professionals, as well as some construction and utility workers. AFSCME, firefighters, and police participated, but later withdrew. The Teamsters have never participated (Wolfson, AAUP-AFT, President; Novosielski, HPAAE, Co-President, 2023; Hernandez, CWA 1031, Vice-President). Even though CRU is not entirely wall-to-wall, however, it is not from lack of trying.

During the COVID-19 pandemic lockdowns, CRU jointly bargained with Rutgers to implement a work-sharing scheme whereby some of the better compensated and secure workers accepted voluntary reductions of hours and pay in order to end layoffs of lower-paid and precarious workers, such as food service and adjunct workers. This was a worker-led effort to protect the jobs of less secure workers in a jurisdiction without established work-sharing programs, though temporary government income support programs allowed most of the furloughed workers to make up for lost salaries (Press, 2021).

Prior to this work-sharing agreement, Rutgers won concessionary deals not only from the Teamsters, but also AFSCME, a CRU-participant at the time. These unions agreed to deferred raises and approximately 1,000 layoffs (Wolfson, AAUP-AFT, President; Hernandez, CWA 1031, Vice-President). When CRU got a better deal, they pushed tenaciously to secure it retroactively for AFSCME. In the end, they won modest reductions in layoffs.

CRU activists prioritized AFSCME's participation so concertedly because, of all the Rutgers unions, it most reflects the intersectional inequalities found on campuses, as a disproportionately racialized, female, and precarious workforce:

They're the people who are serving us lunch and cleaning our offices and we have to be in solidarity with them. Some of our biggest demands during the pandemic were around them and protecting them from layoffs. I don't think we can have the kind of formation we want to have, that speaks to the principles we want to speak to, without the AFSCME union in it (Wolfson, AAUP-AFT, President).

When CRU refused to expel AFSCME for bargaining a concessionary deal with the administration outside of the coalition, the firefighters left the coalition in protest (Wolfson, AAUP-AFT, President).

The major obstacle to wall-to-wall organizing has not been the differences between the various job categories, but rather, the different union cultures with which they often overlap. There is consensus among CRU activists that the non-participating unions tend toward service or business unionism (Martino, AAUP-AFT, member; O'Hea, HPAE, Co-President; Hernandez, CWA 1031, Vice-President). They have more centralized, bureaucratic structures that discourage rank-and-file participation within or beyond their own unions. Many of the same dynamics which make racialized and gendered workers more vulnerable to exploitation by employers can also expose them to more hierarchical, unrepresentative union structures and leaders. By contrast, professional workers are more likely to have participatory unions because of a reluctance 'to cede decision-making authority to union staff' (Hurd, 2000, 108).

In union coalitions, participants may run the spectrum from social movement unions to business unions (House and Gray, 2019). Their motivations might be more ideological or more instrumental (Behrens and Pekarek, 2001), and even if the leaders of business unions disagree ideologically with such coalitions, they might nonetheless participate because the collective strength and resources serves their particular interests (Hansen and Krachler, 2024). To maintain these coalitions, however, participating unions must refrain from interfering in each other's internal affairs. As Nowlan (AAUP-AFT, Executive Director) notes, 'We respect one another's internal decision-making processes and assessments.' This is necessary to avoid accusations of raiding or of 'dual unionism,' the claim that an organization is being built parallel to a union so that it can eventually claim to represent its members. But this principle of non-interference can limit coalitions to issues and approaches that fulfill only the lowest common denominator.

Non-interference also cannot guarantee solidarity in the context of inter-union competition, because coalition work might raise the expectations of members in some unions by exposing them to other more participatory union cultures. Indeed, scholars of union renewal note the transformative effect which coalitions can have on participating unions (Tattersall, 2005). Consequently, leaders might nonetheless distance their unions from the coalition: 'You may have somebody upstream of you who's not as excited about you getting random members together and seeing where it goes, versus what's tried and true: go to the table, get your half-a-percent, and call it a day' (Novosielski, HPAE, Co-President).

CRU must also contend with the control exerted by the parent unions of the participating locals. Novosielski (HPAE, Co-President) notes, 'If I was to say, "We're not going to settle a contract in our local until the adjunct faculty gets health insurance," I would get overruled by somebody in my state federation.' Nevertheless, this is not necessarily a permanent constraint on

locals: ‘My state federation would not be telling me what to do if I had 2,000 people behind me who wanted me to do that thing. It’s a very different situation when your members are calling for something’ (Novosielski, HPAE, Co-President). Participating in such coalitions and coordinating union activities through them can make more salient the need to transform each union toward greater capacities for solidarity.

The influence of parent unions and federations is best illustrated by CRU’s unsuccessful attempt to implement more formal structures and bylaws in late 2020. The proposed bylaws retained a high degree of union autonomy, including a data sharing policy intentionally designed to prevent participant information from being appropriated for union raids (CRU Draft By-laws, 2020). This effort ultimately failed when some of the participants, under pressure from their parent unions, argued that passing the bylaws would violate their union constitutions. Soon afterward, AFSCME stopped participating in CRU, likely in response to the attempt to establish bylaws. Some parent unions have even reserved the right to veto their affiliates’ votes on coalition decisions (Nowlan, AAUP-AFT, Executive Director; Novosielski, HPAE, Co-President). As such, CRU continues to function with a high degree of informality.

While this has allowed flexible structures for collaborations, it has also done little to correct persisting power imbalances (Novosielski, HPAE, Co-President). The vital role and corresponding influence of the full-time professors in the AAUP-AFT is undeniable (O’Hea, HPAE, Co-President; Hernandez, CAW 1031, Vice-President). These imbalances have improved, but it is because some of the smaller locals have pushed back in order to gain more of a voice (O’Hea, HPAE, Co-President). For similar reasons, CRU began taking formal meeting minutes and sharing information more consistently (Hernandez, CAW 1031, Vice-President).

CRU has no elected executive, and the majority of its most active participants are union leaders and staff. When formal decisions are made, it is through a ‘one union-one vote’ process, rather than a ‘one person-one vote’ process typical of some workers’ councils (House and Gray, 2019). The coalition does not collect dues and has no staff of its own. This means that CRU, as a union coalition, is more dependent on the participating unions for its continuing legitimacy and resources than a workers’ council would be. Since activists participate in CRU as members of their own unions, not as individuals, rank-and-file activists from non-participating unions cannot be represented within CRU as currently structured. A rank-and-file reform caucus would have to win union leadership first. Non-unionized workers also cannot be represented, though CRU intends to address both issues in the near future (Wolfson, AAUP-AFT, President).

We can situate CRU within Tattersall’s (2005) framework of different coalition forms, which refers to coalitions between unions and non-union organizations, but can be meaningfully applied to workplace-based union coalitions. CRU is more than an ‘ad hoc’ or a ‘support’ coalition, because it goes beyond one-off requests for support, temporary campaigns for a single issue, and an initiating union that dominates the coalition. Rather, CRU is a ‘mutual support’ coalition which extends the common frame of interest, widens the extent of participation, and deepens collective decision-making. For example, instead of eliciting support for improving health insurance policies for a particular bargaining unit, CRU develops a collective demand for a university-wide standard of accessible healthcare for every worker. Nevertheless, CRU has not yet achieved something like a ‘deep coalition,’ which Tattersall (2005) deems the most powerful form for union renewal. Though the coalition would remain the key decision-making body, it

would provide resources and support for cross-union organizing at the rank-and-file membership level so that they can participate more concertedly in decision-making. While CRU has facilitated rank-and-file organizing independently of the union leaderships, it has done so less in terms of CRU's organizational structure and more in terms of the activities it encourages.³

One such activity is information sharing. This is particularly significant when the administration attempts to establish a concessionary precedent with one of the unions, because CRU can coordinate a united front (O'Hea, HPAAE, Co-President). Indeed, participating unions can hold out on an issue, even if it is not a priority for their own members, to prevent a broader race to the bottom (Hernandez, CWA 1031, Vice-President).

CRU also shares resources, such as meeting spaces or dividing attorney fees in proportion to the size of the participating unions (O'Hea, HPAAE, Co-President; Hernandez, CWA 1031, Vice-President). They thereby combine their respective strengths. For example, some have noted that HPAAE and CWA are particularly adept at legislative policy, while AAUP-AFT has robust political education initiatives (Nowlan AAUP-AFT, Executive Director; Gavigan, AAUP-AFT, Executive Council). CRU also fosters collective actions by coordinating attendance at each union's demonstrations and by staging joint rallies, information pickets, and petition campaigns (O'Hea, HPAAE, Co-President).

The coalition also engages in community unionism. Rutgers' New Brunswick campus is in a primarily Latinx community with a high proportion of undocumented immigrants and mixed status families, while the Camden and Newark campuses are in primarily Black communities (Givan, 2021). CRU participated in a local struggle to save a predominantly Latinx middle school from demolition (Wolfson and O'Connell, 2020). It was to be replaced by a new medical facility affiliated with Rutgers University. Ultimately, this effort failed to save the school, but it helped CRU to develop long-term relationships with community organizations. An integral part of the coalition's form of unionism is its commitment to anti-racism.

CRU's community unionism also contributed to the formation of 'Rutgers One,' an organization of students, faculty, staff, and alumni that advocates for high quality public education. CRU and Rutgers One worked to secure two student positions with voting rights on the university's Board of Governors (Rutgers AAUP-AFT, n.d.c). Wolfson (AAUP-AFT, President) sees this as a preliminary step toward a radically different structure for university governance: a works council that would include student representation.

A number of activities have also spread organizing knowledge and practices far beyond leaders and staff. Hundreds of rank-and-file members have participated in regularly scheduled 'strike schools,' inspired by the 'deep organizing' methods of the American labour organizer, Jane McAlevey (2016). Although they teach strike tactics, the schools occur even when no strikes are imminent, and also include trainings on broader organizing skills and university power dynamics (Pope, 2024). CRU also offers political education to university and community members. The Freedom School, whose program is modeled on the Highlander School, Student Nonviolent Coordinating Committee, and the Black Panther Party, includes sessions on Rutgers' budget model, anti-racist politics, and the Presidential election (Wolfson and Murch, 2021; Gavigan, AAUP-AFT, Executive Council).

CRU has also encouraged deeper rank-and-file participation through the adoption of 'open bargaining': instead of conducting collective bargaining with a small team of

representatives behind closed doors, regular union members are mobilized to participate in the negotiations. This was a case where CRU's information sharing proved particularly important, because of the university's penchant for giving conflicting information to different unions (Holden, CIR-SEIU, staff; Novosielski, HPAAE, Co-President). In a prior round of bargaining, Rutgers repeatedly denied attempts by some unions to introduce open bargaining. When AAUP-AFT attended a bargaining session with non-bargaining team members anyway, the university relented and continued negotiations. The union immediately shared this with other unions, who then acted likewise (Novosielski, HPAAE, Co-President). CRU's organizational form and its coordination of these activities proved crucial in the 2023 Rutgers strike.

The 2023 Strike as a Structure Test

In April 2023, years of organizing culminated in the first Rutgers strike in more than three decades and the first ever by its academic workers. Strikes are the ultimate structure test of workers' 'power and collective organization' (McAlevey, 2016, 34). As such, the strike provides a unique opportunity to assess CRU's strengths and shortcomings. While the general consensus among union members and the media was that the strike won a 'breakthrough victory' (Pope, 2024), it also revealed important divisions and weaknesses.

The strike was made possible by concerted renewal efforts by academic workers toward social movement unionism. After a disappointing round of bargaining in 2018, the AAUP-AFT created a more robust university-wide steward structure and a Contract Action Committee that developed a strike readiness plan (Pope, 2024; Gavigan, AAUP-AFT, Executive Council). This opened space for greater rank-and-file participation. In the part-time faculty union, a rank-and-file reform caucus won leadership after campaigning for greater member participation and militancy.

CRU also laid important groundwork for the strike. The coalition encouraged the synchronization of bargaining timelines to increase their leverage (Wolfson, AAUP-AFT, President; O'Hea, HPAAE, Co-President). Furthermore, during the COVID-19 pandemic, when Rutgers initiated joint briefings with campus unions, the unions pressured the administration to agree to a single ongoing CRU bargaining table for university-wide issues, such as improving workplace health and safety and expanding healthcare coverage (Holden, CIR-SEIU, staff; Nowlan, AAUP-AFT, Executive Director). CRU thereby encouraged the participating unions to develop joint demands and envision the collective action necessary to achieve them. Historically, this has been quite rare in the American public sector, in part, because public sector workers have been averse to entering into coordinated bargaining with other unions (Lewin and McCormick, 1981).

This organizing contributed to the joint strike action by three of the CRU unions, the AAUP-AFT, the PTLFC-AAUP-AFT, and the American Association of University Professors—Biomedical and Health Sciences of New Jersey (AAUP-BHSNJ). In this act of solidarity, the part-time lecturers in particular could leverage the structural power of the other unions to raise their own. Nevertheless, it must also be noted that three more CRU unions failed to join the

strike even though they were in a position to do so: the URA, the CWA, and the Committee of Interns and Residents–SEIU (CIR-SEIU). This weakened the strikers’ power and shows the work that CRU must still do to build its wall-to-wall organization.

This reticence by the non-striking unions may have been due, in part, to the Rutgers administration’s declaration that any strike would be unlawful (Han, 2023). New Jersey’s ambiguous public sector labour laws meant that the Governor, Phil Murphy, though a self-described ‘pro-labor’ Democrat, could grant an injunction forcing workers back into the classrooms. Nevertheless, the striking unions rejected Rutgers’ interpretation of the laws and proclaimed their right to strike. They not only rode the education strike wave from West Virginia through Chicago to California and back again. The striking unions embarked on an action that could be precedent-setting for New Jersey’s entire public sector. In doing so, they were contributing to class formation and capacity building. A lot was riding on this strike.

CRU’s community unionism contributed to the widespread support for the strike, particularly its Bargaining for the Common Good (BCG) approach (Givan, 2021; Martino, AAUP-AFT, member). In BCG, unions form alliances with community groups, decide upon common issues, and prioritize these community demands in collective bargaining as a key moment of leverage within a broader campaign. Bargaining class-wide demands has a long history, but this particular approach was popularized by Chicago teachers during their 2012 strike (McCartin, 2016). Rutgers faculty and students as well as members of New Labor, a local immigrant worker centre, attended national BCG conferences hosted by the CTU (Martino, AAUP-AFT, member).

CRU has used town hall meetings and surveys to canvas the community and identify housing, wages, and healthcare as issues commonly shared with Rutgers students and workers (Wolfson and O’Connell, 2020). In one of its most ambitious endeavors, CRU is developing a campaign with students and New Labor to demand a rent freeze for on-campus housing, contending that this would have spill-over effects and reduce rents beyond the campus (Wolfson, AAUP-AFT, President; Martino, AAUP-AFT, member). In the 2023 round of bargaining, however, the academic unions put forward more modest student-centric demands, such as, that students are no longer prevented from registering for classes, accessing transcripts, or receiving diplomas because of unpaid fees, fines, or parking citations (Rutgers AAUP-AFT, 2023a).

Picket-lines drew from considerable community support. Despite university communications urging students to attend class and complete coursework, they were half of all picketers at times (Yi, 2023). Indeed, an iconic image of the strike came from an unlikely source: a photograph of shirtless fraternity members raising their fists in solidarity.

The workplace power of these coordinating unions, particularly in a strategic industry like higher education, provoked the immediate involvement of the New Jersey Governor. His office brokered a framework for a tentative agreement. After five days of enthusiastic picket-lines, the parties agreed to the framework and suspended the strike. The agreement was overwhelmingly ratified.

The strikers made considerable material gains. Full-time professors won wage increases, but in the spirit of CRU’s principles, lower-wage and more precarious workers fared even better, with sessional instructors, graduate student workers, and postdoctoral associates winning increases of 43%, 32%, and 28% over the course of the four-year agreement (Quinn, 2023).

Teaching and Graduate Assistants won improved workloads while postdocs and adjuncts achieved greater job security (Rutgers Office of University Labor Relations, 2023). New equity provisions established, among other things, course releases for faculty who mentor first-generation or underrepresented students (Rutgers AAUP-AFT, 2023a). Rutgers also agreed to stop replacing unionized Rutgers clinicians with non-union workers hired through RWJ Barnabas, a private network of health institutions with which Rutgers has formed a public-private partnership.

Modest gains were also made on BCG issues. The university agreed that students would no longer be prevented from registering for classes or accessing transcripts because of unpaid fees or fines (Rutgers AAUP-AFT, 2023a). The negotiations also resulted in the creation of a Beloved Community Fund, designed to 'aid employees and community members in need' (Pope, 2024). The fund was originally supposed to be jointly funded by Rutgers and the state government, but after the Governor committed \$600,000 annually for the life of the contract, Rutgers reneged (Rutgers AAUP-AFT, 2023c). Nevertheless, the state's contributions will remain.

CRU and the striking unions also had some significant setbacks. CRU's joint demands were left unresolved by the striking unions, who agreed to continue joint negotiations on these issues. The job action also revealed internal divisions within the striking unions, particularly AAUP-AFT. While the tentative agreement was ratified with overwhelming support, a small but vocal minority of graduate workers criticized the unions' decision to suspend the strike before a deal was reached, believing more could have been won (Kumar, 2023). Unfortunately, some criticisms of union leaders on a private messaging channel engaged in sexist and racist abuse. The AAUP-AFT executive issued a public statement denouncing the comments and struck an ad hoc committee to create accountability processes (Rutgers AAUP-AFT, 2023b).

Although these were serious shortcomings, many non-striking union members walked picket lines and attended rallies. Indeed, a group of Teamsters refused to cross picket lines, temporarily halting construction work (Kausch, Roman, and Goldman, 2023). This relatively small act of solidarity points to the possibility that divisions between Rutgers workers, whether in terms of occupation, status, or union culture, are not insurmountable.

Ultimately, the 2023 Rutgers strike not only made material gains, but also built 'cultures of solidarity' (Fantasia, 1988). In this sense, the strike was a victory, albeit one with some significant limits. The strike showed the power of solidarity by different groups of workers who, by law and custom, have been demarcated into separate bargaining units. It challenged the 'professional' identity and status of faculty, which, traditionally, has preserved hierarchies between workers in higher education. It demonstrated the continued utility of the strike, even in an unfriendly legal context, and represents an important assertion of labour rights in New Jersey with implications well beyond Rutgers' campuses. The striking CRU unions proved the power of collective action, developed new organizing capacities, and solidified inter-union and community solidarity for future battles. The strike is most significant as an exercise in class formation and power.

Conclusion

After decades-long declines in American working conditions and union density, and with the persistent competition and conflict between the unions that remain, there have been vigorous debates about union renewal. Workers in those sectors with relatively high union density and militancy have often mitigated, but not prevented, the neoliberal policies and practices that are hastening the decline in their working conditions. This shows that the ‘organizing the unorganized’ perspective, while important, is not sufficient for union renewal. Being unionized is not the same thing as being organized, particularly when there is rampant sectionalism between unions. Social movement unionism correctly emphasizes the kinds of unions being organized and their relations to each other. This perspective seeks to recover the industrial unionism that was prevalent in the American labour movement at its peak, particularly the principle of wall-to-wall organizing. Such a recovery amid neoliberal conditions constitutes a new industrial unionism.

In a variety of sectors featuring large and complex workplaces with multiple unions, workers have pursued wall-to-wall organizing by creating workplace-based union coalitions. These retain the benefits of certified unions while creatively navigating the sectionalism encouraged by American labour laws. These kinds of coalitions do not limit themselves to cyclical coordinated bargaining, though even this is rare in the American public sector. Rather, they build standing organizations capable of developing workplace-wide demands and collective actions. CRU is a key case of such a coalition.

CRU can be particularly effective because the education sector is a strategic industry. Like most of the public sector, it cannot be offshored (McAlevy, 2016). Furthermore, in higher education in particular, workers’ direct actions, especially strikes, can have disruptive effects extending far beyond the campus grounds. University towns are often akin to ‘company towns’ because of the outsized power of these institutions in their communities (Baldwin, 2021). Rutgers, ‘is one of the largest employers in the region, so the economic fortunes of many more people than employees and their families are affected by what happens there’ (Wolfson and O’Connell, 2020). Although this kind of coalition between unions is distinct from coalitions with non-union organizations, it by no means precludes the latter, and even encourages it. This can be seen in CRU’s community unionism, especially its BCG approach. Such intersectional, class-based, worker-community alliances are a particularly viable strategy for higher education workers, given the strategic leverage of their particular workplace power.

Like any ambitious project, however, CRU has weaknesses it will need to address. It remains highly dependent on personal relationships, on union leaders and staff, and on the informal power of particular participants and unions (Gavigan, AAUP-AFT, Executive Council; Novosielski, HPAE, Co-President). Furthermore, CRU is not yet a fully wall-to-wall organization. It has been unable to overcome the divisions between union cultures, especially those between white- and blue-collar workers, and the ways these divisions map onto intersectional inequalities among Rutgers workers. Finally, while CRU pursues joint demands and BCG, as the 2023 round of bargaining demonstrated, it has been unable to maximize the

number of unions participating in coordinated strikes and has not yet made these demands central ‘redline’ bargaining issues.

Despite these limits, CRU’s new industrial unionism has become a national model for campus worker organizing (Gavigan, AAUP-AFT, Executive Council). This form of workplace-based union coalition could be applied throughout much of the education sector, and beyond this, to other large and complex workplaces with multiple established unions, like hospitals, airports, and municipalities (McAlevey, 2014; House and Gray, 2019). This model can make an important contribution to the American labour movement by recovering principles of industrial unionism, overcoming sectionalist divisions, and fostering working class formation.

¹ In the United States, workers gain full collective bargaining rights once they have completed a union recognition process that includes a certification election overseen by the National Labor Relations Board. Successful certification entails the creation of a bargaining unit based on the principle of a ‘community of interest.’ This means that workers in the same workplace with the same employer may be separated into different bargaining units, which will undertake technically separate processes of collective bargaining. In some cases, workers who lack collective bargaining rights will nevertheless form union-like organizations and engage in a range of activities to advance their interests. In other cases, workers with the legal right to collectively bargain may voluntarily forgo the certification process for practical or political reasons (see Lynd, 1992).

² So-called “right-to-work” laws undermine union security by forbidding collective agreements from containing clauses that require workers to pay union dues or agency fees as a condition of employment. Historically, right-to-work laws were common in the southern United States and states with generally weak labour movements. In recent years, a number of states which are more strongly associated with organized labour, such as Wisconsin and Michigan, have passed right-to-work laws. These laws have been found to have a negative impact on union density rates and undermine union power (Murphy, 2023).

³ There are ongoing debates amongst advocates of social movement unionism about the respective roles of rank-and-file workers, union leaders, and staff organizers (McAlevey, 2016; Moody, 2020; Holgate, 2021; Banks, 2021; Brook, 2022). The debates have focused on topics like the extent to which different organizing models are dependent on staff organizers who substitute for, rather than facilitate, organizing by rank-and-file workers; whether staff organizers are more accountable to union leaders than regular members; the extent to which union bureaucracies have interests separate from those of members; and whether reliance on union leaders and staff, as well as the aspiration to ‘supermajority’ participation in actions by at least 90% of union members, discounts the role played by ‘militant minorities’ in advancing struggles throughout the history of the union movement. Although we discuss the relations of rank-and-file workers, elected leaders, and staff in CRU and the participating unions, parsing the nuances of this debate is beyond the scope of this article.

Appendix A: Table of Rutgers Unions

Sector	Union	Groups of workers represented
academic workers in non-medical fields	Rutgers American Association of University Professors-American Federation of Teachers (AAUP-AFT)	full time faculty, teaching assistants and graduate Assistants, postdoctoral associates, Educational Opportunity Fund Counselors
	Part-Time Lecturer Faculty Chapter (PTLFC-AAUP-AFT)	part-time faculty
academic workers in the medical field	American Association of University Professors–Biomedical and Health Sciences of New Jersey	faculty teaching doctors, nurses, and health scientists at Rutgers and Rowan University
	New Jersey Education Association–Rutgers (NJEA-Rutgers)	faculty in the School of Health Professions
	Committee of Interns and Residents–SEIU (CIR-SEIU)	resident physicians and interns at Rutgers and across New Jersey
professional, white collar workers primarily in non-medical fields	Union of Rutgers Administrators–AFT (URA-AFT)	administrative assistants, academic counselors, financial workers, business coordinators
	Communications Workers of America (CWA) Local 1031	supervisors of academic work, maintenance, construction, and environmental services in BHSNJ
	American Federation of State, County and Municipal Employees (AFSCME) Clerical, Office, Laboratory and Technical (COLT) Local 1761	head clerks, classroom and daycare assistants, laboratory and library assistants, pharmacy technicians
professional, white collar workers, primarily in the	Doctors Council–Service Employees International Union (SEIU)	doctors in the Rutgers student health centers
	CWA Local 1040	supervisory employees for health services in the New Jersey Department of Corrections (NJDOC)

medical field	Health Professionals and Allied Employees-AFT (HPAE) Local 5094	professional staff in Rutgers BHSNJ
	HPAE-AFT Local 5089	registered nurses in various Rutgers health institutions
blue collar workers	AFSCME Local 888	custodians, dining service workers, mechanics, maintenance workers, emergency medical workers, security guards, laundry attendants
	International Brotherhood of Teamsters Local 97	facilities, technical, maintenance, and health care staff in the BHSNJ and NJDOC
	Office and Professional Employees International Union (OPEIU) Local 153	security officers and dispatchers in BHSNJ
	International Union of Operating Engineers (IUOE) Local 68-68a	construction, maintenance, utility employees
	IUOE Local 68	HVAC and energy management workers in the BHSNJ
firefighters and police	Rutgers Emergency Services– International Association of Fire Fighters (IAFF) Local 6888	emergency response lieutenants and fire inspectors
	Fraternal Order of Police (FOP) Lodge 62	police officers

Appendix B: Table of Interview Participants			
Name	Union	Position	Date of interview

Gavigan, Ian	Rutgers American Association of University Professors-American Federation of Teachers (AAUP-AFT)	Executive Council (leadership)	14 February 2023
Hernandez, Kathy	Communications Workers of America (CWA) Local 1031	Vice-President (leadership)	06 March 2023
Holden, Sarah	Committee of Interns and Residents–SEIU (CIR-SEIU)	lead organizer (staff)	10 March 2023
Martino, Carmen	AAUP-AFT	regular member	21 February 2023
Novosielski, Ryan	Health Professionals and Allied Employees-AFT (HPAE) Local 5094	Co-President (leadership)	20 March 2023
Nowlan, Patrick	AAUP-AFT	Executive Director (staff)	17 March 2023
O’Hea, Justin	HPAE 5094	Co-President (leadership)	24 February 2023
Tsitouras, Diomedes	American Association of University Professors–Biomedical and Health Sciences of New Jersey (AAUP-BHSNJ)	Executive Director (staff)	24 March 2023

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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